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Intergenerational ethics in land policy: Consequences of unjust planning on Berlin's land market

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Abstract

In Berlin, throughout the last 30 years, sales of state-owned property to reduce the city's debt were defended as a land policy without alternative by policymakers. These solutions in land policy were not discussed as an ethical issue but as pragmatic considerations. This article reframes Berlin's land policy as a wicked problem, an approach justified and critically outlined by multiple risk perceptions and ethics in planning. Ethics in planning and myths of property relations are derived from Cultural Theory (CT). Following this typology, risk perceptions and preferred tendering processes in Berlin's land and real estate policy between 1990 and 2020 will be analysed as monorational re-solutions. Building on a literature and policy review, as well as 20 expert interviews, this article examines today's expectations towards land policy and identifies five periods of monorational re-solutions and their waves of intergenerational consequences for present and future generations. To illustrate intergenerational injustice in land policy, according to CT, the article puts forward a typology of risk perceptions in tendering processes.

Keywords

land policy, intergenerational justice, cultural theory, tragedies of property myths, wicked problems

Intergenerational consequences of land policy

Since the financial crisis in 2008, there is an increasing international debate in real estate studies on the financialisation of land and housing markets. This debate is most concerned with today's rising prices in land, construction, and rents—and the effects of gentrification and segregation. In Germany, this debate goes back to Vogel (2019), who argues since the 1970s that private property profits which are the result of planning decisions are not taxed appropriately. Moreover, once state property is sold to private owners, any increase in the land value by the demand for land and housing is privatised. But as long as cities are shrinking, followed by a drop in demand for housing, local government can use privatisation of state

property to reduce state debt. Furthermore, this way they keep up with the rising costs of public infrastructures.

Still, for development of public infrastructure state property is needed. Today active land policy is one of the key planning strategies in urban development (German Institute of Urban Affairs, 2021). In recent years, multiple organisations call upon growing cities to re-purchase both private property and former state property from the land market in order to expand welfare-oriented urban planning. It is also suggested, like Vogel advocated for in the 1970s, that profits resulting from planning decisions would be communalised in the future (Building Land Commission of the Federal Ministry of the Interior and Community, 2019; German Academy for Urban and Regional Planning, 2019; Adrian et al., 2021, Bündnis Bodenwende, 2021).

In the wake of the financial crisis, planning on state property was perceived as the ideal of just land policy. Supposedly not as affected by the financialised tendencies of land market as private property, state property is seen as the safe haven for future generations' land policy needs. Building on the active and lively debate on a just land policy for future generations in Germany, this article looks back at previous generations' supposedly unjust land policy in Berlin.

Unfortunately, ideals of just planning often remain ethically implicit in planners' worldviews (Müller, 2017). This implicitness contributes to pragmatic and "monorational" planning solutions (Davy, 2012, p. 200). However, the pluralistic society of the 21st century offers an infinite number of norms, perceptions, hence, rationalities. It is thus necessary to accept that planning becomes complex, uncertain and normative: Its problems are not simple, but essentially "wicked". To respect normative pluralism, planning needs to find "polyrational" solutions (ibid.). Monorational planning solutions tame problems rather than disentangle their normative perceptions, and over time tame solutions lead to "wicked problems" for future generations (Rittel & Webber, 1973).

Categorising normative risk perceptions according to "Cultural Theory" (CT) (Douglas, 1999; Thompson et al., 1990; Thompson et al., 1999), Davy (1997, 2004, 2008, 2012) developed cultural theory into a "theory of polyrationality" to use it in spatial planning and land policy. He focuses on the siting of hazardous facilities (1997), regional governance (2004), and the impact of property relations on the use of rural and urban land (2012). Hartmann applied the theory of polyrationality to responsive land policy and flood management (2011) and public participation in planning (2012). As well, Hartmann and Hengstermann (2014) analysed polyrationalities in the European cohesion policy and Schmitt and Hartmann (2016) in urban design. Building on the philosophical roots of the theory of polyrationality from Davy (1997), Hartmann (2018) defined four explicit ethics in planning: utilitarianism, social justice, liberalism, and environmental ethics.

Most important for this article, Davy (2012) used the theory of polyrationality to categorise and analyse the normative wickedness of land policies in terms of “tragedies of property myths”. In these tragedies, generations of land use planners present mostly monorational “re-solutions” (Rittel & Webber, 1973, p. 160) to the recurring problem of achieving just land policies: They “overinclude” one of the four ethics and its property myth and “overexclude” the others (Davy, 2012). As a result, present-day generations’ wicked problems are symptoms of former generations’ monorational re-solutions. Therefore, monorational re-solutions perceived as ethically just may have unjust intergenerational consequences.

This article sets out to explore such unjust consequences arising from land policy in Berlin. The second section discusses how in pluralistic society, land policy is “essentially unjust” (Davy, 1997). Here, the case is made for an intergenerational perspective on ethics in land policy. The third section presents an intergenerational critique of the round table of Berlin’s real estate policy (*Runder Tisch Liegenschaftspolitik Berlin*), which can be considered as present day “negotiation format” (Hartmann, 2012) for land policy in Berlin. This negotiation format was initiated by civil society actors. To get accustomed with the competing actors and organisations of Berlin’s land policy, I attended four round table meetings as a guest and participating observer between November 2019 and October 2021. For a deeper understanding of the competing rationalities, I conducted 20 expert interviews, ranging from the round table’s coordination team and moderator to state and district politicians, bureaucrats, scientists, and activists. As it is crucial to listen to the ethical critique of competing “expectations” (Hartmann, 2012) in planning processes, the research on the round table was the starting point for this article on Berlin’s land policy.

Based on civil society’s expectations of just land policy voiced at the round table and a literature and policy review, the fourth section presents risk perceptions and monorational re-solutions from different negotiation formats of Berlin’s land market between 1990 and 2020. In the fifth section, these re-solutions and their unjust intergenerational consequences are discussed in terms of ethics in planning and the corresponding tragedies of property myths.

Essentially unjust ethics in land policy: Tragedies of property myths

In pluralistic societies, problems of land policy are wicked. When adding an intergenerational perspective to these problems, they become even more so. Tamed by planners’ implicit worldviews (Müller, 2017), they often present simple solutions as the one solution to a given problem. But this one-dimensional surge for solutions can only ever offer monorational re-solutions. In application, they mostly fail to solve wicked problems definitively. In the future, “waves of consequences” will expose the “bad” effects of solutions that are unsustainable in normative terms (Rittel & Webber, 1973, p. 163).

As many much-cited social science classifications prove, society is more complex as the tenets of individualism and essentialism suggest (Verweij et al., 2020). In reference to cultural theory, actors and organisations shaping land policy can be understood as a reflection of pluralistic society. Pluralistic societies offer an infinite number of different risk perceptions—as well on land policy. Several scholars have proposed to reduce this variety to four “rationalities” (Schwarz & Thompson, 1990) and categorise them into the “grid-group scheme” (Gross & Rayner, 1985; Douglas, 1982, 1987, 1999; Thompson et al. 1990; Thompson et al. 1999; Schwarz & Thompson, 1990): In “egalitarianism,” individuals organise with high solidarity and low stratification. In “hierarchism,” individuals organise with a strong group reference and high stratification. “Individualists” organise with a low group reference and in equally low hierarchies. In “fatalism,” there is a high group reference to the network of stratification and a low reference to group solidarity.

According to the “impossibility theorem” (Thompson et al., 1990, p. 87), the dividing lines of social conflicts can be drawn universally along these four rationalities. For this reason, it is impossible that all four rationalities are not simultaneously represented in social situations. On the contrary, it is more likely that the “situational dynamics” are even more complex and that even further ethics are present.

Subsequently, several authors (Davy, 1997; Hartmann, 2012, 2018; Schmitt & Hartmann, 2016) note that to this day planning is influenced by three major measures of justice: utilitarianism, liberalism, and social justice. Hartmann (2018) defines these, as well as environmental ethics, as the dominant ethics of planning. These ethics overlap substantially with the three dominant rationalities: “utilitarianism” (= hierarchy), “liberalism” (= individualism) and “social justice” (= egalitarianism).

In this regard, the ethics in planning tell four different “policy stories” (Thompson & Rayner, 1998a, 1998b), comprising the setting of a problem, guilty villain, rescuing hero, and moral of history. According to Davy (2012), three tragedies of property myths can be told in accordance with these policy stories. Though subject to the specific context, in varying situational dynamics the roles are largely set: “the community,” “individual landowners,” and “the government” (Davy, 2012, p. 11). In the following three myths, the cast refers to each other in their mutual critique of (un)just property relations. The descriptions below are derived to a great extent from Davy’s work on injustice in land policy (2012, pp. 11–36).

In the first policy story, “Rousseau and the myth of similarity” (Davy, 2012, p. 18), the community of farmers is promised equal access to pastures and fields for all their farm animals. They own the pasture collectively. Individual areas do not exist. As soon as everyone increases their grazing to increase their personal profit, the pasture fails to recover and declines. The community—this is the “tragedy of the commons” (Hardin, 1968; Ostrom, 1990)—cannot control individual enrichment. Rights and duties of land use cannot be guaranteed. Only in small projects can local groups manage themselves. If the projects grow,

all farmers reap the benefits but neglect their duties. This way, land use is not efficient. The land use of the collective limits the individual freedom to own land. When this tragedy affects the community of farmers, they turn over the management of land use to stratified planning hierarchies (Wegener, 2012).

The next policy story, “Hobbes and the myth of control” (Davy, 2012, p. 15), focuses on expertise, a comprehensive claim to control, and high legal security (Albrechts, 2004, pp. 744–745). The government can provide infrastructure and determine which land uses are in the public interest. Its development plans outline locations and extents of land use. This myth is followed by the “tragedy of the government” (Davy, 2012, p. 13). Taxes must be increased because of the expansion of the administration's powers. Communities and individual landowners who want to change land use must apply to the authorities for building permits. The volume of requests can only be processed slowly by bureaucratic systems. Until then, individual plots of land remain unused. Utilitarian planning cannot plan the desired land uses efficiently enough, costs too much, and restricts the freedom of individual landowners. In addition, state planning could be prone to corruption and non-transparency. In the community of farmers' and individual's perspective, the government cannot justly balance land uses.

In dissent, the farmers return to the myth of similarity. For them, self-government is still the perfect solution. And thus, they would decentralise land use to small spaces. Here, isolated communities of common ideals preserve duties towards nature and society (Ostrom, 2007). The answer of individualists, on the other hand, is a free land market, divided into individual plots and clear ownership structures, granting individual landowners the freedom to choose the best land use.

In the third policy story, “Locke and the myth of liberty” (Davy, 2012, p. 16), a promise is made to prioritise economics in planning (Sorensen and Day, 1981) and to preserve trading of land use rights. Each landowner can exclude overuse since the rights of use are clearly limited (Demsetz, 1967). What is new about this liberal ideal is that fences and walls cut through former public roads. Other owners and their livestock are disconnected from rivers and pastures. As soon as these boundaries are further reinforced, the “tragedy of the individualist” (Davy, 2012, p. 13) emerges. Big landowners exchange their land use for factories or settlements. This will restrict the peasant community's ability to keep farm animals. Some herds will no longer have enough grazing land and their farmers will eventually be forced to sell their land, work in factories, and move to the settlements.

In total liberty, if big landowners are not constrained in their ambitions by governments, negative consequences for the community can arise. Land might be accumulated, monopolised and the market power in land ownership exploited. In this scenario, individual land is not available for public goods. Pluralistic property relations,

essential for a world of infrastructural interdependence, are made impossible by an exclusively free land market (Talmadge, 2000).

The fourth ethic, fatalism, never dominates such policy stories over property myths. In general, fatalists reject social contracts from the outset. For them, land policy is too wicked to be solved justly. In their perception, wickedness itself is the tragedy. Any re-resolution is not a quest for justice, but a gamble in planning. Neglected as a counterproductive planning paradigm in collaborative planning, one can argue that fatalism is needed in land policy as well: For example, through biocentric environmental ethics (Hartmann, 2018) nature can be assigned an intrinsic value. It is therefore entitled to rights—without any use for humankind. On some plots of land, like nature reserves, no ethical competition of human re-resolutions is the most just solution.

Each monorational myth for itself, the cast members re-solve the wickedness of land policy. As shown, in their ignorance of pluralism, they are locked in a cycle of critique once they overexclude others' rationalities. Table 1 summarises monorational policy stories about land policy.

Table 1: Four monorational policy stories about land policy

Rationalities (Douglas, 1987; Thompson et al., 1990)	Egalitarianism	Hierarchy	Individualism	Fatalism
Ethics in planning (Hartmann, 2018)	Social justice	Utilitarianism	Liberalism	Environmental ethics
Property myths (Davy, 2012)	Myth of similarity	Myth of control	Myth of liberty	Rejection of a social contract
Tragedies of property myths (Davy, 2012)	Tragedy of the commons	Tragedy of the government	Tragedy of the individualist	Tragedy of wickedness
Property regimes (Davy, 2012, p. 161; according to: Bromley, 1991, 2006; Needham, 2006)	Common property	State property	Private property	No property

To shift the debate, solutions to these tragedies could be formulated not as perfect ones but as “clumsy solutions” (Verweij et al., 2006), or “polyrational land policy” (Davy, 2012).

Polyrational land policy respects three key points:

1. Each land policy actor has experiences and risk perceptions that the others do not.
2. It distinguishes between four fundamental ethics in land policy, their myths of just land policy, and desired property regimes.
3. To provide normatively sustainable re-resolutions to wicked problems, the four ethics must be seen as interdependent. As demonstrated by the tragedies of property myths—

i.e., conflicts of monorational overinclusion and overexclusion—arise when only one or two rationalities are considered in formulating problems and re-solutions.

The typology of polyrational land policy facilitates an inter-ethical learning process between actors and organisations of different monorational risk perceptions. In the justification and critique of re-solutions to wicked problems, they engage in an exchange about the fact that land policy is essentially unjust.

This article argues for the incorporation of an intergenerational perspective to use the typology of polyrationality to analyse injustice between generations of planning actors. Therefore, the next section presents this exchange on Berlin's land market in 2021. First, points of contention from the case study of the round table of Berlin's real estate policy are summarised. The aim is to thereby highlight the intergenerational consequences that must be dealt with today. Second, re-solutions that have been applied in the past and have led to these consequences are presented. This two-tier approach is essential to clarify the question of "what is [and was] the right thing to do?" (Sandel, 2009) in Berlin's land policy.

Collecting today's critique: The round table of Berlin's real estate policy

Since state property for public infrastructure is scarce, Berlin's land market in 2021 is heavily contested. On the few remaining plots in state property, many land uses conflict with each other. Often, the same plot in state property must meet the spatial demands for a district's new school, new public housing, growing city administration, collaborative housing projects, and neighbourhood initiatives. Many dedicated actors and organisations of civil society and the political opposition see this scarcity of land as the result of 30 years of *wrong* land policies. The state's real estate management is met with particularly loud criticism. It is under control of the senate department of finance (*Senatsverwaltung der Finanzen*) (SenFin). In this department, land is regarded as an asset that can be converted into cash.

In response, engaged actors of civil society founded the round table as the most recent negotiation format within Berlin's land policy. The roundtables are expected to bring the needs of local citizens to the attention of policymakers. First discussed in 2011 by the civil association *Initiative StadtNeudenken* (ISN) (2011a), Thiel (2012, p. 3) called for "dialogical land policy negotiations" among representatives from politics, administration, science, and civil society. Indeed, since 2013, this negotiation format evaluates the *good* and the *bad* of 30 years of land policy in Berlin. Additionally, 33 public meetings until end of 2021 served to develop new normative perspectives and explain the specifics of Berlin's land policy to a wider audience for the first time (ISN, 2011b, 2021).

At the round table, a wide range of actors—from neighbourhood initiatives to NGOs; from districts representatives to state politicians; from bureaucrats of municipal offices to international investors—openly voiced opposing expectations on land policy. Prima facie, at the round table meetings many citizens complained about individual problems, such as the

rising rents in their inner-city neighbourhood, the scarcity of land for housing, commercial and art spaces, or the hindrances of civil engagement created by city politics. Some brought forward NIMBY positions: “The city’s real estate in my street should not be sold to the highest bidder—otherwise the neighbourhood will be gentrified.” On the other hand, collaborative housing projects at the round table demanded that municipal properties should be sold to them through concept tendering (*Konzeptverfahren*) in ground lease (*Erbbaurecht*) instead of best-bidding processes (*Bestbieterverfahren*).

According to Berlin’s land policy schemes, in bidding processes, the selling price of a property is not predetermined, but adjusted according to the offers of the interested parties. Decisive for contract conclusion are the highest offer and the customer's proven ability to pay. With the sale, land property ownership is transferred with all rights (BIM, 2021a).

In contrast, ground lease allows for real estate and land use to be separated from the property ownership. This way, private buildings can be built on state property. For a previously agreed period (e.g. 99 years), the property owner rents out the building right. This contract includes all rights and obligations of managing the land. In return, based on the property’s value, the public institution receives an annual rent (BIM, 2021b).

In combination with ground lease or property sale, concept tendering is used for the user-oriented allocation of state property to private institutions. The best concept is established in a competitive procedure. Hereby, the quality of the submitted concepts, usually consisting of development, usage, and ecology concepts, is evaluated. Even though of secondary importance, the purchase price offered is included in the allocation procedure (BIM, 2021c).

To clarify circumstances of tendering processes of real estate policy to civil society, the round table’s coordination team made attempts to increase the transparency of land policy by inviting policymakers. They underlined these efforts with two workshops, one on the topic of ground lease (ISN, 2017) and another on concept tenders (ISN, 2019). Both were organised by the coordination team in cooperation with the senate department of finance to bring experts’ and citizens’ knowledge together. This way, the team aimed for a higher degree of transparency in tendering practices to help increase citizen involvement in the future.

The isolated complaints on land policy by local neighbourhood initiatives, NGOs, collaborative housing projects, and small and medium enterprises rallied under one central headline: “In Berlin, there is not enough land and real estate available for affordability in housing, commercial spaces, and arts.” Therefore, over the past eight years (2013–2021), the main demand at the round table was for Berlin’s House of Representatives (*Abgeordnetenhaus Berlin*) to pass a law on a moratorium on the privatisation of municipal land and real estate (ISN, 2012). At least in the German context, it is unprecedented that a negotiation format, initiated by civil society, proposes a policy re-solution regarding land policy on the state level. From a longitudinal perspective, the round table is built on

intergenerational critical expectation: Why is there not enough land and real estate to secure affordable living and working in Berlin?

Underlining this critique, one politician of the Left Party pointed out: “Today there is no land because all the land was privatised in the past! Whether it was profitable or not, I don't care!” In another interview with a Green politician, the solution was formulated as follows: “The mistakes of the past must not be repeated.” When I took this statement to other interviews and asked for mistakes of the past and of the root of the scarcity of land, interviewees made quite different points of contention: “It was the Social Democrats' fault!” or “It was the Christian Democratic Unions' fault!” were two often stated problem formulations along party political lines. Of course, during the 30 years of reunified Berlin, all democratic parties were involved in the government's land policy in one way or another. This circumstance raised questions: Did the political parties involved perceive different risks of land policy? Can the problem formulation of land policy reach beyond party politics? Many interviewees of neighbourhood initiatives and collaborative housing projects answered this question on societal structures by pointing to the neoliberal market and its impact on real estate management. Other political insiders reasoned that “Berlin's corruption is the root of all problems.” As the Berlin bank scandal in 2001 is seen by some as a foreshadowing of the financial crisis in 2008 at Germany's state level (Ugarte Chacón & Krüger, 2006), corruption, perceived through fatalism, is also a part of the pluralism in land policy.

What is not surprising, however, is that various actors—politicians, activists, bureaucrats—defined different years as the “problematic past” ranging from the early 1990s to the present. In respect of five periods, they discussed different negotiation formats and their attempted solutions as “the root of today's problems in land policy.” At the end of the interview series in August 2020, it seemed like former negotiation formats did not solve land market problems but rather produced them. The ominous mistakes of the past can be seen as monorational risk perceptions that did not include future risk perceptions. The implicit world view of planners in charge were not balanced out by competing expectations. Certainly, these mistakes of the past relate to risk perceptions that actors do not agree with today. In 2020, participants of the round table framed past solutions as injustices that were seen as just solutions in their time.

These expectations represent today's perspective to the intergenerational lens onto land policy. Based on these empirical findings, the following questions guide the fourth section: What were the risks of land policy? What risks did various negotiation formats—in the 1990s, 2000s, 2010s—perceive in the attempts to re-solve problems of Berlin's land policy justly? And what are the intergenerational (un)just consequences to these re-solutions?

Under intergenerational critique: Monorational re-solutions of Berlin's land policy

This section presents the five most referenced negotiation formats from the literature review as normative re-solutions in Berlin's land policy between 1990 and 2020. All of them have been widely discussed in the literature and expert interviews, but they have not yet been considered jointly in an intergenerational context:

1. The coordination committee for inner-city investments (*Koordinationsausschuss für innerstädtische Investitionen*), active between 1990 and 1995.
2. The new public management reform of Berlin's budgeting (*Berliner Budgetierung*), law in force since 1995.
3. Berlin's real estate fund (*Liegenschaftsfonds Berlin*), active between 2001 and 2015.
4. The privatisation of Berlin's non-profit settlement and housing association (*Gemeinnützige Siedlungs- und Wohnungsbaugesellschaft*), in 2004.
5. The transparent real estate policy (*Transparente Liegenschaftspolitik*), law in force since 2013.

1990-1995: The coordination committee for inner-city investments

After German reunification, West Berlin was in possession of the land markets of a new—formerly German Democratic Republic—inner city. A surge of investment in these markets was intended to transform the inner city in terms of urban development and economic terms, to pay off debts of the reunification and finance a clean start as Germany's capital. To manage the development effectively, the committee was founded in 1991 as an “overarching administrative unit for large investors willing to build” (Lenhart, 2001, p. 133). East Berlin was neither legally nor administratively prepared for a free market economy, and thus, international investments were coordinated in this informal body. Here, the highest administrative authorities of the federal government and the state of Berlin convened with the purpose to simplify the unsettled property relations in the eastern inner city—for reasons of privatisation.

For Lenhart (1998), the committee failed democratic policy as it operated without parliamentary control. The committee was criticised having no anchor on the constitution and no ties to Berlin's House of Representatives. Its decisions were never legally binding and could therefore be challenged by large investors seeking to override urban planning requirements. Legal protection of the right of the state and districts was omitted in the planning process. When it came to privatisation of common property, the committee solely made use of the planning instrument of direct award (*Direktvergabe*). Thereby, each plot of state property is offered to a single interested investor. This way, investors did not have to bear the risk of competition for the best bid (Lenhart-Roth, 2020).

Since 1995: Berlin's budgeting

Berlin's administrative reforms of the 1990s were guided by the model of a debt-free state. Therefore, Berlin competed in a business-like fashion with other metropolises for corporate investment by reducing tax revenues (Holm, 2020). A vital component of this was the so-called asset activation policy from 1995 onwards. The senate department of finance used this policy to attract investment in state property. In 1995, Berlin's budgeting, the performance-oriented new public management reform with its cost-benefit calculation (SenFin, 2021a), replaced the revenue-expenditure accounting. Until then, urban development was determined by administrative and political content (Holm, 2020). On the one hand, in best-bidding processes, the districts were able to generate considerable amounts of money for their budget. On the other hand, the sovereignty of district policies was limited by the "compulsion to sell" (Thiel, 2012, p. 11).

Now, the districts must sell off state property in order not to be burdened by their calculative costs. Overall, such cost-benefit calculations led to a 'race to the bottom' of districts selling out their land assets even in debt-free periods. Thus, austerity policies were no longer bound by constraints. Rather, the neutrality of the reform was considered a political instrument to introduce a liberal entrepreneurial technocracy and utilitarian austerity policy to urban development (Lebuhn, 2007a, 2007b; Silomon-Pflug & Heeg, 2013).

2001-2015: Berlin's real estate fund

As a result of the Berlin state bank scandal in 2001 the state's debt increased (Ugarte Chacón, 2012). In the aftermath, Berlin had to consolidate its budget: the goal was to reduce the debt level and net new debt by increasing revenues, reducing expenditures, and reforming public services. For land and real estate liquidations, Berlin's senate established a real estate fund in the legal form of a city-owned subsidiary in 2001 (LFB, 2011, 2015). In line with cost-benefit calculations, Berlin's districts were pressured to hand over their land and real estate assets to the fund (Heuer, 2013). Financial incentives from the senate's department of finance prompted the districts to divest themselves of assets in state properties.

Until 2015, this has led to unprecedented sales of state property. The plots for which are now lacking for public infrastructure like social housing, administrative buildings, schools, day-care centres, sports grounds, cultural facilities, or scientific and research institutions. Silomon-Pflug and Heeg (2013, p. 1) therefore see Berlin's real estate fund as an example of the "neoliberal reorganisation of urban administrations." The fund's sales practices have led to speculation, monopolisation of rental housing stocks, and limited power of action of the public sector on Berlin's land, real estate, and rental housing markets.

In 2004: The privatisation of Berlin's non-profit settlement and housing association

In Berlin's excessive debt situation, extensive privatisations had to be carried out since the mid-1990s. The privatisation of municipal services and the Berlin state bank is often criticised as the liquidation of "Berlin's silverware" (Ugarte Chacón & Krüger, 2006, p. 1). The privatisation revenues were supposed to be used to quickly reduce the state's debt and minimise maintenance costs. In the course of this shift from public to private infrastructure, Berlin's House of Representatives decided to privatise the non-profit settlement and housing association (SenFin, 2004). Subsequently, the state became liable for the profit guarantees of the investors.

Holm (2020, p. 101) considers the privatisation of the association to an international financial consortium for two billion euros in 2003 as a fiscal "taboo break in housing policy." It was the first municipal housing association in Germany to be sold not only with respect to its housing stock, but as an entire company (Holm, 2019). Thiel (2012, p. 5) criticises the often-quoted justification that "Berlin is shrinking and does not need the housing" as a "short-sighted prognosis," particularly because the metropolitan policy of the 1990s was already designed for strong population growth.

For years, the extreme budget emergency was the main risk perception of state policy. Despite privatisation revenues of over 10 billion euros, Ugarte Chacón and Krüger (p. 1120) already in 2006 pointed to the doubling of public debt between 1996 and 2006. With the wave of privatisation, Berlin's senate deliberately neglected drastic social implications, enumerated by Holm (2019, p. 19) as "conversion pressure and rent increases, abandonment of low-market segments without replacement, reduction of municipal distribution resources and the sacrifice of secondary effects of a municipal housing economy."

Since 2013: The transparent real estate policy

Through the excessive sales of state property and real estate, Berlin lost large parts of its urban housing stock. Social housing in particular—formerly subject to occupancy and rent control—was privatised: According to Holm (2020, p. 103), almost 320,000 flats, amounting to 54% of the stock of the state-owned housing associations, were sold. Because there was almost no state-owned building land left, Berlin's House of Representatives reformed the state's land policy in 2013 (SenFin,; 2013; 2019; SenFin in Thiel, 2012). According to the administrative needs of the senate administrations and the districts, the remaining 5,700 state properties were categorised. As a result, "maximising revenue for the benefit of Berlin's over-indebted budget [was] no longer the primary goal" (LFB, 2011, p. 9) of Berlin's land policy.

Shifting back to administrative needs, the instruments of ground lease in concept tendering, and the right to pre-emption (*Vorkaufsrecht*) to buy back needed private property from the free market were expanded (BIM, 2021d, 2021e; SenFin, 2021b). What can be emphasised, this concept is a step forward from the sole logic of land liquidation.

Implementing the transparent real estate policy, at least among the state's administrations it was now transparent what state property was needed for.

The senate department of finance still overseeing land policy, the concept further codifies the privatisation of state property through liquidation and austerity policy. If properties are awarded through direct award or concept tendering, a "city return" must be achieved which compensates for the monetary loss of a potential best-bidding process (Thiel, 2012; Silomon-Pflug & Heeg, 2013). In doing so, the concept was a normative compromise between necessary urban development and budgetary objectives. In following this compromise, the administrative departments of housing, social policy, and education were integrated in the strategic planning of real estate management.

After decades of land policy, some scholars argue that Berlin needed a full internal modernisation that would balance financial and administrative norms. According to Huber (2011), Thiel (2012) and Silomon-Pflug and Heeg (2013), both Berlin's real estate fund and the new estate policy only implemented that in rudimentary terms.

Reframing Berlin's land policies as tragedies of property myths

Over the span of 30 years, Berlin's senate introduced five grand re-solutions of land policy. Using market-liberal tendering processes, the main goal was to escape the risk of budget emergency. Not only are these re-solutions defended by their representatives as "having no alternative," but, as one bureaucrat explained to me, the intergenerational criticism of their opponents is also without alternative. In land policy, there are more risk perceptions than debt and more ethical solutions than market freedom. In the review above, re-solutions of Berlin's land policy between 1990 and 2020 were criticised as market-oriented, investment-friendly, and not democratically justified. The fundamental critical voices in social science discourse show that Berlin's land policy was not *right* nor *wrong* at all, but—supposedly—normatively *bad* rather than *good*. As shown in the second section, especially the term "neoliberal land policy" (Silomon-Pflug & Heeg, 2013) is used synonymously with sharp criticism of the state's *wrong* and *bad* land policy. If neoliberal land policy is *wrong*—and has been the norm in Berlin for over three decades—the following questions might arise: How were these monorational risk perceptions justified and ethically criticised? How did monorational property myths become tragedies?

Taking a fine-grained look at the ethical dimension of past risk perceptions, this section applies the typology of property myths to analyse wicked problems of Berlin's land policy. In the same typology, intergenerational critique is analysed as overexcluded risk perceptions. Based on the hypothesis of the impossibility theorem and an intergenerational perspective, the history of Berlin's land policy will be re-formulated in a chronology of ethical property myths and their respective tragedies. Risk perceptions and preferred tendering processes of real estate policy are determined as core issues of re-solutions in state land policy. Drawing on

the intergenerational critique towards the five grand re-solutions by the round table, interviewees, and literature, the risk perceptions of Berlin's land policy will be quantified. Across periods, this contributes to scrutinise the property myths of past negotiation formats.

After the end of Berlin's special status as a subsidised city, from the Federal Republic of Germany to West Berlin and from the German Democratic Republic to East Berlin, between 1990 and 1995 extensive investments were needed to cover the costs of reunification (SenFin, 2020). In addition, Berlin faced a significant loss of population in the 1990s with suburban migration to the Brandenburg region and internal migration to western Germany (Amt für Statistik Berlin-Brandenburg, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c). In this decade of emigration, Berlin's senate used land policy as a financial re-solution to reduce the skyrocketing debts of public treasury. Since 1995, Berlin's new public management reform perceived selling state property as a re-solution in terms of cost-reduction.

Despite emigration issues, in the first years of reunification the new inner city of the reunified German capital had to be rebuilt. State property was sold cheaply to private actors to include needed infrastructure into their properties. Following the example of the 1994 land use plan, Berlin's new inner city was realised in large parts by project-led urban development (SenS, 2002; SenSU, 1994). In line with the myth of liberty, the coordination committee for inner-city investments sold most properties via direct award to attract investments. It perceived a lack of investments as the highest risk in land policy.

In what can be characterised as an interplay between the myth of liberty and the myth of control, the real estate approach of best-bidding processes between 2001 and 2015 and the privatisation of Berlin's non-profit settlement and housing association in 2004 mainly solved debt problems. Of course, the budget situation was dramatic—and was therefore perceived as the highest risk. Nonetheless, Berlin's debt in 2020 was six times higher than that of 1990 (SenFin, 2020; SenSW, 2021). Berlin needed to consolidate, but sales in state property and real estate contributed only a small proportion to debt reduction: After decades of debt prevention, the revenues of state properties and housing sales between 1990 and 2020 were equal to just 3% of Berlin's debt level in 2020 (*ibid.*). Admittedly, potential future costs for maintenance are not considered by critical voices against the liquidation of state property. In their view, up to 21 km² of state property are permanently lost due to privatisations (Schüsckke, 2020). Official data fall short of this calculation. According to them, approx. five km² of state property were sold between 1990 and 2020. And still, this equates to the privatisation of an estimated 31% of Berlin's financial land assets (SenFin, 2019; SenSW, 2021).

This period is when the tragedy of the government started to unfold. Following a liberal rationality, Berlin's senate sold 364,580 social housing flats between 1990 and 2019—a decrease of 23 percentage points in 30 years (SenS & Investitionsbank Berlin, 2002; Investitionsbank Berlin, 2020). The liquidation of state properties and housing led to a loss of

control on the real estate market—a market with increasing demand for housing. For the first time since 1993, Berlin faced a positive change in population between 2000 and 2003 (Amt für Statistik Berlin-Brandenburg, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c). In times of a re-growing population, the government was incapable of acting.

Since the financial crisis in 2008—a global tragedy of the individualist's free market—and the following zero-rate policy of the European Central Bank, interest rates in stockings decreased. Consequently, in the European debt crisis, financial actors escaped from the bear market and invested in housing and office buildings. During this period investments in Berlin's land and real estate market skyrocketed. Because low interest rates are a substantial risk in investment, land and real estate, particularly in German metropolises, became a solid investment, e.g. for insurance companies (Geoffrey, 2012).

Berlin's senate first started to shift away from its budget-oriented land policy in 2013. Late in the tragedy of the government, the risk of loss of control over the land market was perceived to be higher than the risk of public debts. As mentioned above, in the past 30 years, Berlin's land and real estate assets shifted from state to private property at a scope ranging from five km² (SenFin, 2019; SenSW, 2021) to 21 km² (Schüschke, 2020), depending on sources. With the increasing demand for investment opportunities by the financial market and due to the strong population growth since 2011 (Amt für Statistik Berlin-Brandenburg, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c), prices for land and housing also increased (Berliner Mieterverein, 2013). Further effects of the lack of resilience during the financial crisis in today's land policy can be seen in the scarcity of land in Berlin's districts. As concluded in the second section, every plot of state property must meet multiple spatial demands—from state and district administration to housing as well as common property for civil society.

For the first time in 2013, the transparent real estate policy was formulated in a way, which can be understood as a re-resolution that introduces the myth of similarity into Berlin's land policy. It did not only focus on debt—especially in times of the European debt crisis—but also on generating land for future subsidised housing and public infrastructure. As described earlier, for this very purpose, the instrument of ground lease in concept tendering was expanded.

In the same period, further, the senate department of finance intensified the right to pre-emption to buy back the needed private property from the free land market (SenFin, 2021b). Unfortunately, a tragedy of the commons started around 2011 with the state's dependence on Germany's debt brake (SenFin, 2021c)—an intergenerational legacy of the European debt crisis. Under this national policy, cities are prohibited from taking on debt. States are restricted in taking on new debts. For both, cities and states, even today there are limited public funds available to buy back the needed private property for public land uses such as schools, kindergartens, and social housing from the post-financial crisis market (Senatskanzlei, 2021).

Table 2: The periods of the cycle of tragedies of property myths for Berlin's negotiation formats of land policy

Rationalities (Douglas, 1987; Thompson et al., 1990) Ethics in planning (Hartmann, 2018) Property myths (Davy, 2012) Predominant risk perceptions	Periods Negotiation format	Monorational re-solution Tendering processes of state property	Intergenerational critique	Tragedies of property myths (Davy, 2012)
Individualism Liberalism Myth of liberty - State's debt - No investments in inner city development - Berlin should grow	1990–1995 Coordination committee for inner-city investments	Attracting investors for inner city of the new capital Direct award	- No control by parliament - Tendering not legally binding	Tragedy of the individualist
	1995– Berlin's budgeting	New public management Best-bidding process	- Austerity policy over district's needs for land and real estate - Loss of state property	
Individualism Liberalism Myth of liberty	2001–2015 Berlin's real estate fund	Attracting private development Best-bidding process	- Neoliberal technocracy - Sell-out of the city - State property is now lacking for social housing and public infrastructure	
Hierarchy Utilitarianism Myth of control - State's debt - Berlin will not grow	2004 Privatisation of Berlin's non-profit settlement and housing association	Privatisation to reduce state's debt and minimise maintenance costs Best-bidding process	- Population growth was underestimated - Liquidation had marginal impact on debt level - Nearly no social housing stock and state property left - Loss of state's control over the land market	Tragedy of the government
Hierarchy Utilitarianism Myth of Control	2013 Transparent real estate policy	construction concepts are evaluated in terms of monetary value new focus on land charge and right to pre-emption Concept tendering Land charge Best-bidding process	- Codification of monetarisation of non-fiscal urban development concepts - Since the EU debt crisis, land and housing stock is too expensive to buy back	Tragedy of the commons

Conclusion

By discussing the longitudinal case of Berlin, this article shows how intergenerational tragedies of property myths become trapped in a “cycle of tragedies” (Davy, 2012, p. 35): For Berlin’s land policy, it seems that strong polyrational planning is near to impossible today because only monorationality was implemented in the past. Especially by overexcluding egalitarian rationalities, this led to a liberal dead end in land policy.

At present, the non-resistance of the land and housing market to the financial crisis shows that the monorational waves of consequences can hit later generations with unintended momentum. Yet, the future of Berlin’s land policy is bounded by the Germany’s national debt brake. In 2020, Berlin’s House of Representatives initiated a new land trust with the objective of buying back private property from the free land market. But instead of being able to expand Berlin’s right to pre-emption, the state’s trust is restricted by its compliance with the debt brake. Its scope of action must make do with a limited budget of 250 million euros per fiscal year (Senatskanzlei, 2021). After 30 years of mostly liberal re-solutions, Berlin’s inflated land market cannot be brought under control with this minimal budget.

To summarise, Table 2 categorises the periods of the cycle of tragedies of property myths for Berlin’s negotiation formats of land policy. For each negotiation format, predominant risk perceptions, monorational re-solutions, and preferred tendering processes are presented. Pluralistic intergenerational critiques towards these re-solutions are included as well. In doing so, this article proposes a typology that not only covers the debate that land policy is essentially unjust but also clarifies how divergent risk perceptions can be used to understand intergenerational consequences of tragedies of property myths.

Repeatedly, attempts were made to re-solve the wickedness of Berlin’s land policy—often by employing monorational property myths. These myths, however, seem to have failed. For, today’s generation of planners tries to re-solve the land problems of previous generations’ tame solutions. The historical case of Berlin’s land policy shows that wicked problems are not solved on polyrational grounds but by political economic power struggles and their implicit “pragmatics of planning” (Rittel & Webber, 1973). Applying an intergenerational perspective on the injustice in land policy, this article made the monorationalities behind these pragmatics explicit: For generations of Berlin’s land policy, the risk of debt reduction can be placed at the monorational centre.

Analysing civil society’s intergenerational expectations in the wake of the financial crisis and a growing population in Berlin, this article demonstrates that the sole risk perception of debt reduction ethically was neither effective nor sustainable. Gaining insights from the round table of Berlin’s real estate policy, future’s risk perceptions of establishing land reserves in state property for public infrastructure—and, through concept tendering, common land uses—could be considered to greater extent.

In Davy's terms (2012), today's land policy in Berlin, even though not ignoring pluralism anymore, is locked in a cycle of tragedies. After 20 years of mostly best-bidding processes of state property, in midst of a post-financial crisis land market, Berlin's government is constrained in their more pluralistic ambitions by private landowners. For debt reduction, state property was sold and accumulated as private property: a decade long shift in property regimes on the state level. Through all periods, liberal market power was overincluded. After 30 years of liberal monorationality and simultaneously increasing debts, today, private property is unaffordable for public infrastructure. In consequence, overexcluding egalitarian rationalities in the past, led to a liberal dead end in land policy today.

In the future, it might be necessary to ask even further whether the wicked problem of Berlin's land policy is located only at the state level, or whether there are obstacles created by EU and federal legislation, national and regional economic forces, or the increasing internationalisation and financialisation of land and real estate markets that made the state's land policy essentially unjust. Under such multilevel pressures it will remain a complex challenge to find just solutions in terms of intergenerational polyrationality which are essential for a world of infrastructural interdependence.

Consequently, it is important to look at repetitions of monorational re-solutions in the past and their ethical criticism in order to find out what polyrationality in future land policy might look like. This article proposes such a perspective. Indeed, taking a lesson from the history of Berlin's monorational re-solutions, also means listening to the voices of intergenerational expectations: What are the multiple risk perceptions of polyrational land policy—in the present, in the near, and distant future? One day, the land policy of the 2020s and its property myths should not be associated with restrictive consequences but with an awareness of intergenerational opportunities for future pluralistic land uses.

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